

Fuel oil contaminated ecosystems treatment using microbiological preparation in combination with dispersants based on humic substances and natural raw materials

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Fuel oil (FO) is a heavy fraction of oil with high viscosity and resistance to biodegradation, which, entering the ecosystem (soil, sand, water), disrupts its physico-chemical and biological characteristics, reduces water and air exchange, inhibits microflora and disrupts the circulation of substances. Large fuel oil spills: Norilsk in 2020 - 21 thousand tons into rivers and tundra soils; the Black Sea in 2024 - 4.5 thousand tons led to severe environmental consequences and economic damage amounting to hundreds of billions of rubles. Currently, special attention is being paid to biological methods of cleaning oil-polluted ecosystems based on the use of destructive microorganisms, in particular, bacteria of the genus *Rhodococcus* (including the BioOxOil biological preparation (BOO) based the strain *Rhodococcus degradans* H33) [1].

In the present work, laboratory experiments were conducted to study the effect of microbiological preparation in the presence of dispersants based on natural compounds (including humic substances) on reducing fuel oil concentrations in sand and water. In samples taken from oil-contaminated areas of the Black Sea coast sand (February 2025), the concentration of FO was 3; 5,0; 8,4; 15,5; 33,0 (g/kg). The experiment was carried out for 60 days for sand and 10 days for water. The microbiologics used were the preparation BOO and the microbiological comparison preparation «LenOil» (LO), sodium humate obtained from lignite (SH), thermally modified sapropel (SP), a dispersant based on sulfonated lignin (DSL), a dispersant based on methyl esters of coconut oil fatty acids (DCM), and It is also a dispersant based on inorganic salts, phosphates and carbonates (DIS). The effect of biologics and dispersants investigations on the FO concentration reducing in water were carried out at an initial fuel oil concentration of 3000 mg/l.

The efficiency increasing of fuel oil contaminated seawater purification was measured in the series:

DIS (35.4 %) < LO (57.3%) < BOO (71.2 %) < DSL (71.8 %) < DCM (76.4%) < LO + DIS (80.1%) < LO + DCM (86.3%) < LO + SH (87.3%) < SH (88.4 %) < BOO + DCM (88.5%) < BOO + DIS (90.1%) < LO + DSL (90.3%) < BO + SH (91.9%) < BO + SP (92.3%) < BO + DSL (92.7%).

Investigation of the effect of microbiologics in combination with dispersants on reducing the concentration of fuel oil in coastal sand samples have shown that for all variants, the effectiveness increases in the range of «LenOil» (21.5-49.2%) < «BioOxOil» (28.2-69.7%) < «BioOxOil» + DIS (34.9-72.5%) < «BioOxOil» + DSL (38.3-77.4%).

Thus, «BioOxOil», modified with a dispersant based on sulfonated lignin, showed the best efficiency for both water and sand - 92.7%. The performance of the «BioOxOil» preparation modified with a sapropel-based dispersant (containing a significant amount of humic substances) is slightly lower - the effectiveness is 92.3%, and sodium humate is 91.9%.

1. Patent №. 2759662 C2 Russian Federation, IPC C12N 1/20, C02F 3/34. Bacterial strain *Rhodococcus degradans* H33 ac-2901D - oil and petroleum products destructor : №. 2021121501 : application 07/19/2021 : published 11/16/2021 ; applicant AVIAKHIM Limited Liability Company.